

Casuietry, Listening and Remembering: Three Potentially Anticolonial Psychoanalytic Practices

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Psychoanalysis is part of the same culture that colonially subjugated our world. Colonization prepared the ground for the Freudian legacy to be established outside Europe. If this legacy makes sense to non-Europeans, it is because they were previously Europeanized.

It is due to past colonialism that today we have psychoanalysis outside Europe. Psychoanalysis is an expression of the culture that colonized us, but not of its colonizing face, not of its expansive and invasive inclinations, not of its arrogant and self-assured attitudes. All of this is not what is displayed in the Freudian discovery.

What is discovered with Freud is rather the crisis of modern European culture, the externalization of its pathology, its contradictions that tear the subject apart. To deal with this, psychoanalysis does not seek to overcome the cultural crisis, but to assume the truth that it reveals. Proceeding in this way can have anti-colonial effects, as I will now try to show by examining three psychoanalytic practices: casuistry, listening, and remembering. Let's start with casuistry and its challenge to European universalist pretensions.

Casuistry

Universalism is one of the main ideological justifications of coloniality. The colonizing culture uses its particular perspective as a universal standard to judge other cultures and to justify their colonization. This strategy can take the form of the hypothetic-deductive method, in which we start from a universalized hypothetical European conceptualization that seeks to validate its universality in other particular cultures.

For example, Laubscher¹ in South Africa and Ritchie² in Rhodesia, in present-day Zimbabwe, aimed to verify the universal scope of the Freudian hypothesis of the role of projection in paranoia when they believed they deductively detected paranoid structures and projective mechanisms in Africans. As if by chance, Africans appeared as beings prone to projection and therefore paranoid, which served to explain why they felt persecuted by Europeans. This persecutory experience of colonial violence was interpreted as a projective delusion of the Africans themselves, who, characterized by their supposed paranoia and by the evils they supposedly projected onto Europeans, would logically need to be dominated by the colonial power.

Laubscher and Ritchie express their racist-colonialist prejudices through Freudian rhetoric. These prejudices, however, contradict fundamental principles of psychoanalysis. One of them is the case-by-case analysis.

Freudian casuistry has anticolonial potential because it prevents us from proceeding like Laubscher and Ritchie did when they ignored both psychic singularity and cultural particularity. Freud's consideration of each case should turn our attention to each culture and not just to each subject. Casuistry would thus have to prevent us from not only overlooking the differences between subjects and diagnosing entire peoples as paranoid, but also from generalizing Freudian metapsychology to understand subjectivity in other non-Western cultures.

Between cultures as between subjects, there is what Lacan described as an "absolute difference" that must be "obtained" by psychoanalysis.³ Freudian casuistry can have anticolonial effects by making us recognize that different cultures, with their respective symbolic systems, subjectify us in *absolutely different*, incomparable ways, without

1 Barend Jacob Frederick Laubscher, *Sex, Custom and Psychopathology: A Study of South African Pagan Natives* (London: Routledge, 1937).

2 John F. Ritchie, "The African as Suckling and as Adult: A Psychological Study," *Rhodes-Livingstone Papers* 9 (1943), 1-61.

3 Jacques Lacan, *Les quatre concepts fondamentaux de la psychanalyse* (Paris: Seuil Poche, 1990), 307.

there being a common measure to compare us by relativizing our differences. In reality, each culture and each subject only has its own perspective, its own language, absolutely different from any other. Hence, we cannot account for our differences, since there is no metalanguage through which to place ourselves outside of everything and relativize our differences by defining them *in relation to* the different cultures and subjects.

The absolute difference, a difference as insurmountable as it is indefinable and unobjectifiable, should dissuade us from applying the categories of European culture to non-European cultures. This application, as Bhabha has shown us, requires denying the very difference that is recognized, denying it through a typically fetishist perverse process, that of Freud's *Verleugnung*, which underlies the negative "stereotypes" of subjects belonging to other cultures.⁴ Instead of accepting that subjects of a certain culture are absolutely different from us, we see them as relatively unequal, more or less intelligent than us, with more or less mental health.

Seeing the others as relatively unequal to me is a way of both accepting and rejecting their absolute difference in a typically perverse way. This colonial racist perversion reduces the other subject to the phantasy of being the same as me, but less than me, being only a part of what I am. The other is conceived as having less of the same intelligence, a fraction of the same mental health, a part of who I am.

Seeing the non-European as a piece of the European makes the former practically the same as the latter, "almost the same, although not quite," according to Bhabha's famous statement.⁵ The Asian, the African or the Latin American appear ultimately as a piece of the European Big Other, as its partial object, as its objet petit *a*, as it happens to the Jews in the anti-Semitic visions elucidated by Regnault.⁶ In anti-Semitism, as in other forms of racism, the racialized subject is in the place of the object that is missing and surplus, that provokes desire and anxiety, fascination and repugnance.

4 Homi Bhabha, *The location of culture* (London: Routledge, 2004), 106-108.

5 Homi Bhabha, "Of mimicry and man," *October* 28 (1984), 126.

6 François Regnault, *Notre objet a* (Paris: Verdier, 2003).

The appearance of the non-European as an object is the ultimate result of what Fanon described as a “mutilation of the colonized by the colonial regime.”⁷ Colonialism mutilates us so deeply that it deprives us of our own subjectivity, not by taking away a piece of us, but by transforming us into the piece, into an object of the European Big Other. This Other becomes the only place for us as subjects: the place of our lack, of our castration, of our hopelessly colonized desire, which is alien to us.

Listening

The place of the European Big Other is imposed as the only place, as a space that encompasses all existing spaces, as an *Other of the Other*. If Freudian casuistry demonstrates the nonexistence of this metalanguage, it is because it knows how to listen to each subject. When listening, the psychoanalyst only listens to a language, to an Other, without there being a way to get out of it, or to signify it from the outside, from an *Other of the Other*, from a metalanguage constituted by second-order signifiers that would signify the first-order unconscious signifiers, turning them into meanings, into conscious ideas. Instead of imagining what subjects consciously have in mind and want to say, the psychoanalytic method teaches us to listen to what they say, even when they say it unconsciously. This is how psychoanalysis, by listening, converges with decoloniality.

The decolonial turn precisely recognizes that European civilization cannot provide us with a universal metalanguage capable of signifying the particular languages of different cultures. Quijano is clearly rejecting the European prerogative of an *Other of the Other* when he opposes “the claim that the specific worldview of a particular ethnic group be imposed as universal rationality, even if such ethnic group is

7 Frantz Fanon, *Les damnés de la terre* (Paris: La Découverte, 2002), 146.

Western Europe.”⁸ The same rejection of metalanguage underlies the gesture by which Castro-Gómez condemns the “zero-point *hubris*” by which one believes one has “a point of view about which it is not possible to adopt any point of view.”⁹ This belief in the Other of the Other is also discarded by Grosfoguel when he excludes the “possibility of knowledge beyond time and space,” knowledge of a subject without “sexuality, gender, ethnicity, race, class, spirituality, language or epistemic location.”¹⁰ The delocalized and dematerialized subject is the only one we are allowed to be, but it is a faceless mask, an empty abstraction, an ideological fiction, a colonial simulation of a real subject.

The only real subject with the right to be such in the colonial world is the European, whether as a European or as an American, an Israeli or a member of the white elites in the Global South. Outside of Europe and its extensions, as Quijano has stated, “non-European cultures cannot be or shelter subjects,” but “they can only be objects of knowledge and practices of domination.”¹¹ One condemns oneself to being an object when one presents oneself as non-European, while one’s colonial Europeanization attempts to achieve the condition of subject, albeit alien, or alienating.

To be a subject is, first of all, to be a speaker. Speaking is essential to exercise one’s subjectivity. However, as Spivak has noted, the colonized “cannot speak.”¹² They can only speak as a European, in European terms, in modern, scientific, secular, democratic terminology. Non-Europeans cannot speak in their own terms. Silencing them is a way of preventing them from existing as subjects.

8 Aníbal Quijano, “Colonialidad y Modernidad/Racionalidad,” *Perú Indígena* 13, no. 29 (1992): 20.

9 Santiago Castro-Gómez, *La hubris del punto cero* (Bogotá: Pontificia Universidad Javeriana, 2005), 18-19.

10 Ramón Grosfoguel, “Descolonizando los universalismos occidentales,” in *El giro decolonial* (Bogotá: Siglo del Hombre, 2007), 63-64.

11 Quijano, “Colonialidad y Modernidad/Racionalidad,” 16.

12 Gayatri Spivak, “Can the subaltern speak?,” in *Colonial Discourse and Postcolonial Theory*, ed. Patrick Williams and Laura Chrisman (New York: Columbia University Press, 1994), 104.

Another way of making the existence of subjects impossible is the refusal to listen to their words. Even when they speak, non-Europeans are not listened to by a European hydra that only listens to itself, that only monologues with itself and with its American, Israeli or Australian mouths. This hydra only listens to itself, even when it talks about us, because, as Stuart Hall pointed out, Europe “does not stop talking, does not stop talking about us,” which implies a “power game.”¹³ We are *spoken objects* instead of *speaking subjects*. We are silenced instead of being listened to.

Listening is a second potentially anticolonial practice of psychoanalysis. Freud has taught us to listen to what cannot be listened to, to what has no right to speak, as is the case of the non-European. We know that this usually remains silenced, buried and suffocated in African, Latin American or Asian subjectivity, not being perceived even by the very subjects that it inhabits, whose Europeanized perception is usually insensitive, deaf to any word other than the European one. As Luis Villoro observed, Western reflexivity prevents the non-European from “appearing clearly to consciousness” and makes it remain “hidden in the depths of the mestizo self.”¹⁴ Even the indigenous may have difficulty perceiving the indigenous within themselves.

To perceive the non-European subject, it is first necessary to recognize it as someone who speaks. This requires adopting a method like psychoanalysis, a method based on listening to the subject, instead of the empiricist-positivist epistemological paradigm of the objectifying gaze that reigns in psychology, which reduces speaking subjects to mute objects. Turning the non-European subject into an object of objective European knowledge is a process that make it possible to transform the subject into an object of colonial power.

13 Stuart Hall, “Cultural Identity and Diaspora,” in *Identity: Community, Culture, Difference*, ed. Jonathan Rutherford (London: Lawrence & Wishart, 1990), 232.

14 Luis Villoro, *Los grandes momentos del indigenismo en México* (Mexico City: FCE, 2005), 273.

In the 18th, 19th and 20th centuries, Europe colonially dominated the same peoples it exhibited in engravings, showcases, exotic pictures, and ethnological museums. This exhibition occurred, significantly, at the same time as that of the sick in body and soul in the amphitheatres of hospitals and universities. In both cases, science tried in vain for the visible to encompass everything, including that which resists any vision.¹⁵

There are some things that cannot be seen by the scientific eye. While this gaze objectively scrutinized the tumours, hysterical contortions and images of the aborigines, Freud broke with objectivity and ventured into the invisible. He listened to the words of the subjects silenced by science, thus teaching us a listening that today we can consider potentially anticolonial not only by attending to the subjects as speaking subjects, but also by attending to them as silenced, repressed subjects.

Psychoanalysis teaches us how to listen to the silence and not only the word, the repressed and not only the authorized, the desire of the colonized and not only its reality imposed by the colonizers. The Freudian method is thus distinguished from the positivist approach, which, as Martín-Baró critically warned, ignores “that which the existing reality denies, what does not exist, but that would be historically possible, if other conditions were met.”¹⁶ The possible and denied, to the extent that it is desired, can be discovered through psychoanalytic listening.

Listening to what is denied allows us to subvert what denies it. Three subjective ideological forms through which coloniality operates can thus be subverted, namely, the *ego*, the one, and identity. Let’s quickly address each of them.

The subjectivity imposed by colonization is that synthesized in the Cartesian *ego cogito* in which Dussel¹⁷ has unravelled an *ego conquiro*,

15 Viviana Melo Saint-Cyr, “Rembrandt contra el cientificismo hipermoderno,” *Teoría y Crítica de la Psicología* 3 (2013), 102-115.

16 Ignacio Martín-Baró, “Hacia una psicología de la liberación,” in *Psicología de la liberación* (Madrid: Trotta, 1998), 289-290.

17 Enrique Dussel, *1492: El encubrimiento del Otro* (Madrid: Nueva Utopía,

a conquering *ego*, an *ego* empowered by capitalism and its ideological devices, including psychology. Perhaps this modern European *ego* is convincing to the psychological gaze, but not to psychoanalytic listening. It is enough to listen to subjects to realize that they are not only ones, *egos*, but others contradicting themselves. Their contradictions are also between their colonial condition and what rebels against it. This rebellion is also always against a conquering *ego* that dominates not only the world, but the body and the subjective sphere.

The subject is not only one, but other. This otherness is what we listen to in psychoanalysis. This is what the old Freud¹⁸ emphasized, according to Said, when he attributed an Egyptian origin to Moses, the founder of Judaism and forerunner of Christianity.¹⁹ If the Christian one is the Jewish other, the Jewish one is the Egyptian other, while the Egyptian one, as Diop reminds us, is the black African other.²⁰ Non-European otherness always permeates the European one that tries in vain to purge itself of the other. The other continues to resonate and be listened by psychoanalysis. Psychoanalytic listening allows us to listen to the various forms of otherness that Hall detects in the post-colonial condition: being other in the “hybrid,” being in another place in the “diasporic,”²¹ experiencing oneself as other in European “regimes of representation.”²² In all these cases, we confirm what Kusch already told us when dealing with the European “absorbed” and “contaminated” by the non-European in Latin America.²³ The other always absorbs and contaminates the one, the self, the identity.

1992).

18 Sigmund Freud, “Moisés y la religión monoteísta,” in *Obras completas XXIII* (Buenos Aires: Amorrortu, 1997).

19 Edward Said, *Freud and the non-European* (London: Verso, 2014).

20 Cheikh Anta Diop, *Nations nègres et culture* (Paris: Présence africaine, 2007).

21 Stuart Hall, ¿Cuándo fue lo postcolonial?, in *Estudios postcoloniales* (Madrid: Traficantes de Sueños, 2008), 134.

22 Hall, “Cultural Identity and Diaspora,” 225.

23 Rodolfo Kusch, “América profunda,” in *Obras Completas II* (Buenos Aires: Fundación Ross, 1962), 19.

By dealing with identity, psychoanalysis allows us to listen to identification, to what is unfinished, inconsistent, fissured. This listening has been practiced by several Freudian critics of coloniality. Ménil denounced how the Afro-descendant Antilleans, identified with the French colonist, “deny their race, their body, their fundamental and particular passions.”²⁴ Later, Nandy warned about the colonial “identification with the aggressor” among the colonized.²⁵ Now Ayouch promotes a disidentification with which previous colonial identifications can be reversed.²⁶

Memory

By leading us to identification, psychoanalysis makes us go back to the origin of identity. This origin can be colonial, and remembering it can also be subversive to coloniality. We thus arrive at a third potentially anticolonial psychoanalytic practice.

To free ourselves from coloniality, one must first become aware of it, which requires us to remember our colonization. This was well understood by Martín-Baró, who therefore prescribed “memory to perceive what has blocked, oppressed and crushed our people.”²⁷ What has colonized us has to be remembered so as not to perpetuate itself.

An important part of coloniality is due to the repetition of what is not possible to remember. Sometimes it is enough to remember something to stop repeating it, since repetition, as Freud knew well, is an

24 René Ménil, “Généralités sur ‘l’écrivain’ de couleur antillais,” *Légitime Défense 1* (1932), 7-9.

25 Ashis Nandy, *The Intimate Enemy* (Delhi: Oxford University Press, 1983), 7, 68.

26 Thamy Ayouch, *Psychanalyse et hybridité* (Louvain: Leuven University Press, 2018).

27 Martín-Baró, “Concientización y currículos universitarios,” in *Psicología de la liberación* (Madrid: Trotta, 1998), 135.

unconscious way of remembering what is “forgotten and repressed.”²⁸ By erasing from their memory the imposition of European culture, the colonized impose that culture on themselves again and again. They allow themselves to be plundered unceasingly by forgetting the colonial origin of plunder.

Colonization continues by repeating itself in the form of neo-colonialism and coloniality. To avoid this repetition, psychoanalytic remembering can help us become conscious of what is inherent to colonialism and that is unconsciously continued by other means. This is the case, well explained by Quijano, of the past colonial “repression” that today takes the form of “seduction.”²⁹ If Europe continues to seduce us, it is because it still exercises a colonial power that is eternalized because it is unconscious, because it is as eternal as everything in the unconscious.

Making the unconscious of colonization conscious can serve to free us from it. The best way to overcome a colonially induced feeling of inferiority, for example, is the way indicated by Fanon: that of remembering the “*epidermisation*” of inferiority, the “*inferiorization*” of the non-Europeans correlative of the “*superiorization*” of Europeans.³⁰

Needless to say that memory is somehow prevented by repression. This is why memory can only be acted in a repressed, unconscious, symptomatic way, through colonial repetition. Coloniality, with its intrinsically repetitive aspect, is a complex configuration of symptoms in which repressed colonial history returns.

Coloniality is like a great neurotic cultural formation. This is how it was conceived by Glissant, who distinguished in the history of Martinique the phases of neurosis in Freud: trauma, repression, “symptoms,” and “revulsion” towards memory.³¹ The amnesia of the Martinicans, like that of the neurotics, would make them sick with a history that they would suffer passively.

28 Freud, “Recordar, repetir y reelaborar,” in *Obras completas XII* (Buenos Aires: Amorrortu, 1998), 151-152.

29 Quijano, “Colonialidad y Modernidad/Racionalidad,” 12.

30 Frantz Fanon, *Peau noire, masques blancs* (Paris: Seuil, 1971), 8, 75.

31 Edouard Glissant, *Le Discours antillais* (Paris: Folio, 1997), 229.

We would suffer repressed colonial history, suffering its repetitive symptomatic return, for not being able to remember it. Not being able to remember history, much less could we make it. We could only suffer from it in its pathological repetition, in symptoms such as racism, *pigmentocracy*, inequality, dependency and external interference.

An important pathogenic factor of the Global South would then be ahistorical presentism. It would be what Memmi described as a “cultural amnesia.”³² This amnesiac condition can only be cured by remembering the trauma of colonization, but also what preceded the trauma, what the colonizers did not completely destroy.

As an anticolonial practice, memory has to take us along a path like the one already taken by Oswald de Andrade when he tried to recover the matriarchal and communist indigenous origin “against the clothed and oppressive reality inventoried by Freud.”³³ Psychoanalysis teaches us what we must undress to access a wounded, traumatically mutilated original nudity, which cannot be remembered as it was, but must be retroactively reconstituted. This reconstitution of essence can be useful in an anticolonial strategy, but it goes beyond Spivak’s “strategic essentialism.”³⁴ It is not just a deliberate strategy that creates an imaginary essence, but a *historicization* in which the traumatic and pre-traumatic reality of our origin is symbolically elaborated through a historical plot.

32 Albert Memmi, *Portrait du colonisé, précédé du colonisateur* (Paris: Payot, 1973), 131.

33 Oswald de Andrade, “Manifiesto Antropófago,” in *Vanguardias latino-americanas* (Mexico City: FCE, 2006), 180.

34 Spivak, “Estudios de la subalternidad,” in *Estudios postcoloniales* (Madrid: Traficantes de Sueños, 2008), 45.

In Conclusion

Remembering, listening and casuistry turn us towards our history and our origin, towards our word and our silence, towards our singularity and our particularity. What was devastated by colonialism can thus be recovered, at least in part, through psychoanalysis. Although the Freudian legacy is a colonial legacy, it is also potentially anticolonial as it neutralizes some of the effects of colonialism on subjectivity.

The anticolonial potential of psychoanalysis lies more in its practices than in its metapsychological theory. Freudian metapsychology corresponds to the modern European subjective sphere and only makes sense for other subjectivities to the extent that they have been Europeanized by colonialism. What always resists Europeanization can only be misinterpreted by Freudian categories, perhaps even pathologized, as happens in the colonial racist psychoanalysis of Laub-scher and Ritchie.

Instead of applying Freudian metapsychological notions to non-European cultures, we should better investigate the knowledge of these cultures about the subjective sphere. This is what I have tried to do in recent years when studying Mesoamerican conceptions of subjectivity.³⁵ I have thus arrived at either notions astonishingly close to Freud's, or ideas absolutely inassimilable to Freudian theory.

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35 David Pavón-Cuéllar, *Más allá de la psicología indígena. Concepciones mesoamericanas de la subjetividad* (Mexico City: Porrúa, 2021).